

Google Pixel 3 Setup documentation

Date of Setup: 24th October 2023

Setup by: Daniel Knott

Düsseldorf Institute for Competition Economics (DICE)

Heinrich-Heine-Universität Düsseldorf

First: Basic Settings

- Language Settings (English standard, no change)
- Vision settings (no changes made to standard)
- Emergency call option

Continuing with „Start“

Emergency call

Start

Asked for SIM-card and mobile network

- Pressing “Skip”

Connect to Wi-Fi

- Login to University Wi-Fi with student ID
- Connection not possible
- Skip the only option for now
 - Information over the option that are not possible without Wi-Fi

Option to transfer from old phone

- Option to not copy data chosen

Copy apps & data

Transfer your apps, photos, contacts, Google Account, and more. You can choose which content to copy.

Don't copy data

Next

No progress without internet

- Connection with Wi-Fi or mobile data necessary
- Skip → „couldn't sign in“
- Next → „connect to Wi-Fi“

Without Internet no progress beyond this point

Progress with mobile hotspot

- Continuing with a mobile hotspot
- Installation of software updates on the phone

Checking for updates...

Installing updates

Setting up the Google account

- Setting up a new google account – „create account“
- Name: Dice
- Gender: Rather not say
- Birthday 25 April 2000

E-Mail: dicephoneproject1@gmail.com

Password: Dice24.10

Verification via private phone number

Individual Screenshots of the steps were saved but not included in the presentation

The screenshot shows the Google sign-in interface. At the top right, there is a Wi-Fi signal icon and a battery icon. The Google logo is centered at the top. Below it, the text "Sign in" is displayed, followed by "with your Google Account. [Learn more](#)". A text input field with the placeholder "Email or phone" is present. Below the input field are two links: "Forgot email?" and "Create account". At the bottom of the screen, there are two buttons: "Skip" and "Next".

Additional options with Google Account

Asked to add phone number to the account

- More options.

Picked: No, don't add my phone number

Google

Add phone number?

If you like, you can add this phone's number to your account for use across Google services. [Learn more](#)

For example, your number will be used to

- Reset your password if you forget it
- Receive video calls & messages
- Make Google services, including ads, more relevant to you

How it works

- To check that your number is current, Google and your carrier may exchange device info, or use background calls or SMS. Standard rates may apply.
- Any number verified on this device will be added to your Google Account

You're in control

<

Google

Choose what's right for you

- No, don't add my phone number
- Yes, I'm in - add my number for use across Google services
This phone's number will be added to your Google Account and used across Google services (for things like account security, video calls, and more relevant ads). Google will save and occasionally verify your number by exchanging your device info & phone number with your carrier, or by using background calls or SMS (charges from your carrier may apply).
- Add my number for account security only
Add a phone number to make your account more secure, including for password reset.

You can always add a phone number later or control how your number is used in your Google Account (account.google.com/phone).

Back Done Yes, I'm in

<

How it works

- To check that your number is current, Google and your carrier may exchange device info, or use background calls or SMS. Standard rates may apply.
- Any number verified on this device will be added to your Google Account

You're in control

- This won't make your number public
- You can always change your number, control how it's used, or remove it in your Google Account (account.google.com/phone)

[More options](#)

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Review account info

- Creation of the account finished, additional settings available

Review your account info

You can use this email address to sign in later

Dice

dicephoneproject1@gmail.com

Next

Google personalisation settings

- Two options
 - Express personalisation (1 step) → nudging? Picking this option automatically allows for everything
 - Manual personalisation (5 steps)
 - Chosen: manual
 1. Web activity → keep
 2. YouTube history → keep
 3. Ad personalisation → allow all
 4. Privacy reminders → accept
 5. Confirm
 - Privacy and terms → Agree
 - **Account creation complete**
- Screenshots on the following slides

Choose personalization settings

- Express personalization (1 step)
Use personalization settings that deliver tailored content and ads. We'll remind you in a couple of weeks to review your settings.
- Manual personalization (5 steps)
Configure your personalization settings step by step. You decide which settings are on or off to get the content and ad experience you want.

You can change your settings anytime at account.google.com

Next

For faster searching, save your Web & App Activity

Step 1 of 5

Choose whether to save Web & App Activity

- Keep until I delete manually
- Keep activity for 18 months and manually delete any time
- Don't save Web & App Activity in my account

What data is used

Web & App Activity saves your activity on Google sites and apps, including searches and associated info like location. It also saves synced Chrome history and activity from sites, apps, and devices that use Google services.

How we use this data

When this setting is on, Web & App Activity saved in your account may be used in any Google service where you're signed in to give you more personalized experiences when using Google products, like faster searching, more relevant results, and app and content recommendations automatically tailored to you.

For YouTube homepage recommendations, save your YouTube History

Step 2 of 5

Choose whether to save YouTube History

- Keep until I delete manually
- Keep activity for 36 months and manually delete any time
- Don't save YouTube History in my account

What data is used

YouTube History saves the videos you watch and the things you search for when you use YouTube.

How we use this data

When this setting is on, YouTube History saved in your account may be used in any Google service where you're signed in to personalize your experience, like giving you better recommendations when using YouTube and other Google products, for example articles, apps, YouTube homepage recommendations, and videos that pick up right where you left off. When this setting is off, YouTube features that rely on history to personalize your experience are disabled.

..

For more tailored ads, turn on Ad Personalization

Step 3 of 5

Choose whether to turn on Ad Personalization

- Show me personalized ads
Tailors the ads you see based on your activity and other data, and lets you block advertisers or ad topics you're not interested in
- Show me generic ads
You'll still see ads, but they may be less useful, because they'll be based on general factors like the time of day, general location, and content of the page you're looking at

What data is used for personalized ads

We'll tailor ads based on your activity on Google services, such as your queries on Google Search, videos you watch on YouTube, apps you install on your Android device, ads or content you interact with, and associated information like your location. We use information you have provided in your Google Account, such as your age and gender. We'll also use your activity on other sites and apps that use our advertising services.

How we use data for personalized ads

Get occasional privacy reminders

Step 4 of 5

Choose whether you want occasional reminders to take a Privacy Checkup and review key privacy settings

- Choose the types of data we save
- Update what you share with friends or make public
- Adjust the types of ads you'd like to see

Privacy reminders
Get occasional email reminders about these settings

You can change your settings anytime at account.google.com

[Back](#)

[Next](#)

Confirm personalization settings and cookies

Step 5 of 5

- ✓ Web & App Activity
This setting will be turned on
- ✓ YouTube History
This setting will be turned on
- ✓ Ad Personalization
This setting will be turned on
- ✓ Privacy reminders
Occasional email reminders are set

About cookies and IDs

We rely on [cookies](#) and device IDs to remember your settings and other preferences across your signed-in devices. We also use cookies, IDs, and data to

- deliver and maintain services, like tracking outages and protecting against spam, fraud, and abuse

After options are picked: Finalising the account creation

- Asked to accept terms and privacy
- Account creation finished

Privacy and Terms

We publish the [Google Terms of Service](#) and the [YouTube Terms of Service](#) (both of which include information about your 14-day withdrawal right) so that you know what to expect as you use Google services, including YouTube. The [Google Play Terms of Service](#) also applies because Google Play helps manage apps on your device. By choosing "I agree" you agree to these terms.

A Google Account allows you to access a range of Google services, such as Gmail and Google Drive. An account also offers access to some additional features that require signing in. For example, when you sign in to Google Maps, you can save your "Home" and "Work" addresses. And when you sign in to YouTube, you can like videos, subscribe to channels, and create your own YouTube channel. Google's Terms of Service apply to [this list of services](#), a list that also provides links to service-specific additional terms and policies that explain what you can expect from using Google services, and what we expect from you.

And remember, [Google's Privacy Policy](#) describes how Google handles information generated as you use Google services.

It also includes information about why we process data, such as when we are pursuing legitimate interests while applying appropriate safeguards that protect your

- Customising our services to provide you with a better user experience (and, if relevant, adapting the experience to be age-appropriate)
- Marketing to inform users about our services
- Providing advertising, which allows us to offer many of our services at no cost (and when ads are personalized, we ask for your consent)
- Detecting, preventing, or otherwise addressing fraud, abuse, security, or technical issues with our services
- Protecting against harm to the rights, property or safety of Google, our users, or the public as required or permitted by law, including disclosing information to government authorities
- Performing research that improves our services for our users and benefits the public
- Fulfilling obligations to our partners like developers and rights holders
- Enforcing legal claims, including investigation of potential violations of applicable Terms of Service

You can visit your Google Account (account.google.com) to take a Privacy Checkup or to adjust your privacy controls.

Have questions? [Contact us](#)

[Don't create the account](#)

[I agree](#)

Google services

- Back up to Google Drive, Location, Maintenance, automatically downloading updates and apps

→ all agreed to

Fingerprint

- Option to add fingerprint
- No fingerprint added (skipped)
- Screen lock: 1234 (screenshot unavailable)

Unlock with Pixel Imprint

Use your fingerprint to unlock your phone or approve purchases.

Note: Your fingerprint may be less secure than a strong pattern or PIN.

Skip

Next

Continue setup

- Option to finish setup early or continue
- Continue option chosen

Google Assistant: turned on

Voice Match: No thanks

Squeeze: Do it later

No Google Pay added

Notifications added to lockscreen

Nothing else for now

Last tips → all set

- Screenshots follow

Additional Settings - Screenshots

Always-on display

Time, notification icons, and other info will appear on your lock screen

Squeeze for your Assistant

To talk to your Assistant at any time, quickly squeeze the bottom half of your phone, then release

Access your Assistant with Voice Match

Voice Match lets you access your Assistant directly by using your voice, even when your screen is off.

A unique model of your voice will be created on this device, which will help your Assistant identify you and tell you apart from others.

Keep in mind: A similar voice or recording might be able to access your Assistant, too. You can remove Voice Match permission later by turning it off in Assistant settings.

Google Assistant

The new way to talk to Google

Text mom

Help your Assistant customize your experience by turning on these settings.

dicephoneproject1@gmail.com

App info from your devices ▼
Saves information about the apps installed on your signed-in devices to make them easier to interact with when

Anything else?

Set up a few more things now, or find them later in Settings

Add another email account

Change font size

Change wallpaper

Control info on lock screen

Discover songs with Now Playing

Review additional apps

No thanks

Turn on

Do it later

Next

No thanks

I Agree

No thanks

Turn on

No thanks

Home screen

- Visible apps on home screen
 - Phone calls
 - Messages
 - Google Play
 - Google Chrome (!)
 - There was no option to pick a (different) browser
 - Camera
 - Google search bar
 - There was no option to pick a (different) search engine

Initial Layout (screenshots)

- Very few preinstalled apps

First google search

- Search for „dice hhu“

First use of browser (google chrome)

- Agree to terms and conditions – accept all
- Signing in with google account

The image displays three sequential screenshots of the Chrome mobile interface during its first use. The top status bar shows the time as 1:14, 1:15, and 1:15 respectively, along with icons for signal strength, Wi-Fi, and battery.

Screenshot 1 (Left): The "Welcome to Chrome" screen features the Chrome logo. Below it, the text reads: "By using this application, you agree to Chrome's [Terms of Service](#) and [Privacy Notice](#)." There is a checked checkbox for "Help make Chrome better by sending usage statistics and crash reports to Google." A blue button labeled "ACCEPT & CONTINUE" is at the bottom.

Screenshot 2 (Middle): The "Sign in to Chrome" screen offers two options: "dicephoneproject1@gmail.com" with a blue checkmark, and "Add account" with a plus sign icon. A blue button labeled "NO THANKS" is at the bottom left.

Screenshot 3 (Right): The "Hi, Dice" screen shows the user's name and email address. It includes two sections: "Chrome Sync" (with a checkmark) and "Personalize Google services" (with a checkmark). A link "Manage Chrome Sync and personalization in [Settings](#)" is at the bottom. Blue buttons labeled "CONTINUE", "UNDO", and "OK, GOT IT" are at the bottom.

Options in Google Chrome

- Google as standard search engine
- Recommendations for: Facebook, YouTube, Amazon, Wikipedia, ESPN, Yahoo, eBay, Instagram
 - No other browser, but products from other companies (Facebook, Amazon, etc.)
- German and English news about different topics on the home page

Google Play store

- Get started: Certain recommended apps
- Based on recent activity
- Recommended for you
- Popular apps
- Etc...
- Options include other browser (Firefox)
- I did not install anything new

Accessing lists of default apps

- Pressing on Browser: No alternative browsers are shown, no downloads recommended
- Same with assist & voice input
- Payment method: default google pay, no recommended or shown alternatives

Setting up Gmail

- Dice E-Mail already installed

New in Gmail

All the features you love with a fresh new look

GOT IT

Trying to download an app outside of google play store

- Accessing the Fortnite website – downloading for android from epic games (Fortnite creator)
- Download over website not possible
 - Download through chip.de (German technology magazine) (screenshots follow on next slide)

Fortnite - Battle Royale APK - Android App

Version 19.30 | **Rang 0 / 906 bei CHIP** in der Kategorie: **Spiele**

DOWNLOAD
FORTNITE - BATTLE ROYALE APK - ANDROID APP

- ✓ Virengeprüft
- ✓ Kostenlos

Android

Download-Fakten:

Fortnite - Battle Royale APK - Android App	
CHIP Redaktion: Gut	1860 Nutzerwertungen: 3,7
Kompatibel mit Android OS	
Sprache:	Deutsch
Downloadzahl:	1.313.342
Version:	19.30 vom 21.02.2022
Kaufpreis:	Gratis

Partner von:

Fortnite - Battle Royale APK - Android App

Sicheres Herunterladen mit Avira

Download-Server CHIP Online

Download Anzeige

Avast Free Antivirus – 100% Sicher

Der beliebteste Gratis-Schutz - von Chip-Lesern empfohlen. Sicher, schnell und intuitiv. Jetzt herunterladen!

INTERESSANTE DIGITAL-ARTIKEL BEI FOCUS ONLINE

TikTok testet 15-Minuten-Videos

Wolkenkratzer oder Baustelle? Die ersten Wertungen zu "Cities Skylines 2"

Ifo: Personalchefs sehen Künstliche

Necessary changes to settings

- Asked for storage access – granted, allow
- Download progresses – „this download can harm the device“

Further changes

- Have to change settings to open the .apk → allow google to download apps from unknown source
- Installing possible

Fortnite

Fortnite

Do you want to install this application? It does not require any special access.

App installed.

Cancel Install

Done Open

Comparison: Samsung A03-Setup (same day)

(First mentioned slide references the presentation on Samsung A03 core)

- Terms and Services have to be accepted at a later stage with Google compared to Samsung (slide 2)
- Google asks for a SIM-card in between the first step and connecting to Wi-Fi, no restart necessary (slides 2 & 4)
- Obviously, Samsung Account creation is not necessary (slides 13 & 14)
- The Pixel has only Google Chrome as a preinstalled browser, while Samsung has both Chrome and Samsung internet (slide 16)
- Upon opening the Google Play Store, no installation of additional browsers was offered or recommended (slide 19)
 - Additional browsers or search engines were at no point recommended
- External application (Fortnite) could be installed, did not require an application called “Google Go” (slide 23, 24)

Comparison to Samsung Galaxy A03s

(First mentioned slide references the presentation on Samsung Galaxy A03s)

- Terms and Services have to be accepted at a later stage with Google compared to Samsung (slide 3)
- No requirement to give permissions for general preinstalled apps and services like calendar, call logs, contacts, etc. with Google (slide 3)
- Google asks for a SIM-card in between the first step and connecting to Wi-Fi, no restart necessary (slides 3 & 5)
- No suggestion to get recommended apps (slide 11)
- Obviously, Samsung Account creation is not necessary (slides 12 & 13)
- No apps recommended for download (slide 14)
- No games are preinstalled on the Pixel 3 (slide 15)
- The Pixel has only Google Chrome as a preinstalled browser, while Samsung has both Chrome and Samsung internet (slide 16)
- No alternative search engines or web browsers were overtly suggested by Google (slide 19)